

Competence Framework for the Use of Arts in Education to Foster Cultural Awareness and Expression

SUMMARY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Summary | University of Malta (Lead)

1. PURPOSE AND CONTEXT

The PULSE-ART Competence Framework for Cultural Awareness and Expression (CAE) was developed under Work Package 2 as a structured, evidence-based reference tool for educators, learners, higher education providers, and policymakers. The framework operationalises EU Key Competence for Lifelong Learning number 8 “Cultural Awareness and Expression” (European Commission, 2019) by translating it into a coherent, observable set of competences applicable across formal, non-formal, and informal learning settings. It is directly aligned with the Council of Europe's Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC, 2018), the UNESCO Framework for Culture and Arts Education (2024), and the OECD Learning Compass 2030, thereby situating PULSE-ART within the current European landscape of competence-based education policy.

The framework serves a dual function: it constitutes a conceptual model defining what cultural awareness and expression entails across educational contexts, and a practical instrument guiding the design, implementation, and assessment of arts-based learning activities within the project's pilot case studies (WP4) and professional development programme (WP2).

2. METHODOLOGY

The framework was developed through a rigorous, multi-phase methodology that ensured both scientific grounding and practitioner relevance. Phase 1 comprised a comparative analysis of 17 international competence frameworks (2015–2025), selected across four domains: Education (e.g., EU Key Competences for Lifelong Learning, OECD Education 2030), Arts and Culture (e.g., UNESCO Framework for Culture and Arts Education, NCCAS), Digital Technologies (e.g., DigCompEdu, AI in Art Education), and Policy (e.g., Innovative Policymaking and Science for Policy). Frameworks were examined for their competence dimensions, structural organisation, target groups, learning contexts, and progression logic, using a qualitative mapping approach to identify convergences, gaps, and underrepresented dimensions.

Phase 2 comprised participatory co-creation workshops with project partners, initiated at the project Kick-Off Meeting (November 2024). Partners from universities, cultural organisations, and community institutions engaged in case-study mapping, focus group discussions, collaborative competence definition exercises, and feedback surveys. These sessions validated and enriched the literature-based findings, added context-specific competences emerging from local arts-education practices, and established the ethical foundation of the framework through the articulation of seven core values: empathy and emotional intelligence; openness and curiosity; respect and relational ethics; agency and participation; responsibility and reflection; ecological awareness and care; and sense of belonging and joy in learning.

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This summary contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Phase 3 involved partner data collection, including a cross-national policy analysis synthesising arts-in-education practices from seven countries (France, Greece, Latvia, Malta, Morocco, the Netherlands, and Spain), and a partner survey (May 2025) in which all case-study partners rated the relevance of proposed competence areas on a 1-5 scale and described their manifestations in practice. Results confirmed strong validation across all proposed areas (predominantly ratings of 4-5), with the support of the creative process and the creative thinking and artistic inquiry emerging as the most universally foundational competences.

Phase 3 also included a Partner Validation Workshop (September 2025), in which partners used a collaborative Miro board to categorise individual skills, knowledge, and attitudes within a Knowledge-Skills-Attitudes (KSA) structure, producing the empirical basis for defining each competence's scope and interrelationships. Subsequently, an Expert Validation Mosaic Hub (November 2025) brought together seven external specialists in arts education, cultural pedagogy, and competence framework design. This session employed a triangulated data collection strategy combining video recording, chat transcripts, and a structured post-session survey using Likert-scale and open-ended items. The expert panel rated the framework's overall quality as Excellent or Very Adequate and affirmed its theoretical soundness, clarity of descriptors, and applicability across contexts, while recommending refinements in areas such as linguistic accessibility and the stronger integration of cultural heritage dimensions.

Phase 4 synthesised all evidence streams into a unified competence structure, integrating insights from literature, workshops, and national reports. The resulting framework is organised around two interrelated strands and will undergo iterative validation during WP4 pilot implementation, with findings feeding into WP5 (impact assessment) and WP3 (policy recommendations).

3. CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS

The framework draws on four principal theoretical traditions. Socio-cultural and constructivist learning theory, grounded in Vygotskian principles, positions artistic creation as a dialogic, co-constructed process in which meaning emerges through interaction and mediation. Aesthetic and emotional learning theory (Eisner, 2002; Bamford, 2006) treats aesthetic experience as a form of knowing that integrates emotion, perception, and imagination, situating the arts as vehicles for emotional literacy, empathy, and identity formation. Intercultural and democratic education, informed by the RFCDC (2018), positions CAE within a democratic paradigm in which cultural participation fosters pluralism, dialogue, and civic responsibility. Finally, inclusive learning principles (UNESCO, 2005; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011; Banks, 2008) ensure that pathways to cultural awareness and expression are accessible to all learners across the lifespan, grounding the framework's commitment to equity and anti-discriminatory practice.

Building on these foundations and on the PULSE-ART definition of CAE, the framework conceptualises Cultural Awareness and Expression (CAE) as a dynamic interplay of five dimensions: Creative and Reflective Thinking; Cultural Literacy and Intercultural Dialogue; Personal and Social Expression; Collaborative Creation, Participation and Collective Building; and Critical Engagement and Responsibility. These dimensions are scaffolded by the seven core values enumerated above, which serve not as supplementary considerations but as the normative foundation of every competence area.

4. THE FRAMEWORK: STRUCTURE AND COMPETENCES

The PULSE-ART Competence Framework is organised into two interrelated and complementary strands: Learner Competences (L1-L4), articulating CAE, and Educator Competences (E1-E5), defining competences needed by educators to support learners in developing CAE through arts-based learning. Each competence is articulated through three KSA dimensions and described across four proficiency levels (Foundational, Intermediate, Advanced, and Expert) reflecting a developmental orientation that allows progression in depth, autonomy, and reflexivity.

4.1 LEARNER COMPETENCES

L1 Creativity and Reflection addresses learners' capacity to generate original ideas, engage in reflective and ethical creative processes, and solve problems through creative risk-taking and experimentation across artistic media, digital tools, and embodied practices. L2 Cultural Literacy and Intercultural Awareness equips learners to interpret cultural expressions within their social, historical, and intercultural contexts, critically engaging with issues of representation, power, colonial legacies, and cultural diversity. L3 Personal and Shared Cultural Expression centres on learners' ability to express identity, values, and lived experience through multiple artistic and communicative modalities, while also developing the capacity to interpret and position themselves in relation to others' expressions. L4 Collective Agency and Social Responsibility addresses learners' capacity to act collaboratively and responsibly within social, civic, digital, and environmental contexts, engaging in intercultural dialogue, shared decision-making, and ethically grounded civic participation.

LEARNERS COMPETENCES

The framework operationalises the 'Cultural Awareness and Expression' (CAE) competence into four key dimensions, describing the specific capacities learners develop within an arts-based learning environment.

1. Creativity and Reflection

- Generating and developing original ideas through artistic processes.
- Approaching problem solving, risk-taking and decision making in reflective and ethical ways.

3. Personal and Shared Cultural Expression

- Expressing feelings, stories and identities through different art forms.
- Co-creating shared expressions with others, acknowledging and valuing different contributions.

2. Cultural Literacy and Intercultural Awareness

- Understanding how culture, history and power shape expressions and everyday life.
- Showing empathy and appreciation for diverse perspectives, stories and experiences

4. Collective Agency and Social Responsibility

- Using the arts to engage with social, environmental and political issues.
- Responsibility and care in public, digital and media spaces,

4.2 EDUCATOR COMPETENCES

E1 Designing Inclusive and Culturally Responsive Learning Environments focuses on educators' capacity to create accessible, equitable, and culturally inclusive learning spaces that respond to diverse learner identities and needs. E2 Building Creative Processes addresses educators' role in scaffolding learners' creative development across disciplines, supporting idea generation, iteration, and autonomous creative expression. E3 Assessing Cultural and Arts-Based Learning emphasises formative, process-oriented, and ethically grounded approaches to documenting creative and cultural learning over time, respecting the complexity of intangible learning outcomes. E4 Facilitating Intercultural Dialogue and Collaboration focuses on educators' capacity to guide critical analysis of cultural representations, facilitate respectful cross-cultural exchange, and connect arts-based practice with civic and community engagement. E5 Reflecting on Practice and Cultural Positionality addresses educators' critical awareness of how their own identity, background, privilege, and bias shape curriculum choices and classroom interactions, promoting ongoing reflective, collaborative, and anti-discriminatory professional practice.

EDUCATORS COMPETENCES

The Competence Framework for Educators articulates the competences that Educators need to support learners in developing cultural awareness and expression through arts-based learning. These five competences emphasise adaptive, reflective, and context-sensitive practices that respond to educators' and learners' diverse identities, cultural backgrounds, and requirements.

5. SIGNIFICANCE AND NEXT STEPS

The PULSE-ART Competence Frameworks contribute to the European arts-in-education field by offering a dual-audience, evidence-based, and value-driven reference tool that is simultaneously grounded in international policy frameworks and co-created with diverse practitioners across seven national contexts.

In subsequent phases of PULSE-ART, the framework will guide **case study implementation** across seven artistic disciplines and six countries (WP4), inform the development of the **self-reflection tool and impact assessment** instruments (WP5), and underpin **policy recommendations** and national action plans (WP3). It is also embedded in the PULSE-ART [Observatory for Arts in Education](#), where it structures the **mapping of practices, resources, and learning pathways** for broad dissemination across European educational and cultural ecosystems. PULSE-ART Competence Frameworks present high potential for **standardization**.